
EFFECT OF MOTIVATION, WORK DISCIPLINE AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE PT SHARP ELECTRONICS INDONESIA (DIVISION CUSTOMER SATISFACTION)

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Abstract:

This research examines and analyzes motivation, work discipline and organizational culture on the performance of employees at PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (division Customer Satisfaction) that have not been maximized, due to the achievement of the results of performance appraisal in the 2017L and 2018F periods there was a decrease in each assessment indicator which greatly impacted employee performance. The method used is quantitative research. With a population of 110 employees, PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction), with sampling techniques using Slovin formula with a total of 86 employees. The analytical method used in this study is multiple linear regression. The results of the study show that Motivation, Work Discipline and Organizational Culture together (Simultaneous) significantly influence the Performance of Employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction).

Keywords: Motivation; Work Discipline; Organizational Culture; Performance.

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1. Introduction

In the face of competition in the global era companies are required to work more efficiently and effectively. Increasingly intense competition causes companies to be required to be able to increase competitiveness in order to maintain the survival of the company. Employees or employees are the most important element in determining the back and forth of a company. To achieve company goals, employees need to be in accordance with the requirements in the company, and also must be able to carry out the tasks assigned by the company. Every company will always strive to improve the performance of its employees, with the hope that what will be achieved by the company goals. The ability of employees is reflected in performance, good performance is optimal performance.

PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia is one that manufactures electronic products such as televisions, refrigerators, and washing machines etc. With the many products produced by PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia and with the Indonesian market conditions which are very broad, and many customer complaints about sharp products. Where in customer satisfaction division can respond to complaints and requests for customer repairs properly, supported by the customer care center customer complaints and requests can be received quickly. With the number of complaints and requests for improvements from the customer, the performance of employees is currently declining, from the assessment of the 2017F and 2018L KPI (Key Performance Indicator) 2 period there has been a 15% decline.

The results of previous studies that strengthen this research are as follows: first, research by Johannes Elizer (16), said that motivation can certainly affect one's performance. Second, research by Dally Sukmawati (17), the better the discipline carried out by employees, the greater the work performance that can be generated. Third, research by Emma Tampubolon (15), states that organizational culture can have a significant impact on work performance in the long run.

The purpose of the research is to find out as below:

- 1) The effect of motivation on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction)?
- 2) The effect of work discipline on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction)?
- 3) Effect of organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction)?
- 4) Influence together between motivation, work discipline and organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction)?

1.1. Employee Performance

Rivai in Muhammad Sandy (2015: 12) gives an understanding that performance or work performance is the result or the level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as work standard results, target or criteria that have been determined in advance and agreed upon together. So it can be concluded that the success of an employee in his work can be seen from the indicators of whether the employee has completed the task in a timely manner and in accordance with the specified procedure, or the employee completes his work assignment always late from a predetermined schedule.

1.2. Work Motivation

According to Hasibuan (2013: 95) motivation comes from the basic motive word, which means a stimulus, desire, and the driving force of one's will. Motivation is the giving of driving force that creates the enthusiasm of one's work so that they will cooperate effectively and integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Human behavior in its essence is goal oriented, and a person's behavior is generally stimulated by the desire to achieve a number of goals, a person's behavior can actually be assessed based on several basic elements consisting of motivation and purpose.

Motivation is sometimes used alternately with other terms such as needs, desires, drives, and impulses.

1.3. Work Discipline

According to Rivai&Sagala (2013: 825) is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and to increase awareness of a person's willingness to comply with all the rules and social norms that apply in a company.

1.4. Organizational Culture

Robbins and Judge (2015: 256) emphasize "Organizational culture is a system of shared meanings held by members that distinguishes one organization from another.

Based on a review of the theory that has been stated previously, the research hypothesis is proposed by the researcher as follows:

H1: There is an effect of motivation on employee performance.

H2: There is an influence of work discipline on employee performance.

H3: There is an influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

H4: There is an influence of motivation, work discipline and organizational culture together with employee performance.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Type of Research

In this study, this type of research uses a quantitative method approach. According to Sugiyono (2015: 14) quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods that are based on positive philosophy, used to research certain populations, sampling techniques are generally done randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical in order to test the hypotheses that have been set.

2.2. Variable Scale

In this study, the measurement scale used was the Likert scale. Likert scale is a scale used to measure attitudes, opinions and perceptions of someone or a group of people about social phenomena, Sugiyono (2017: 158). Data is obtained by using structured quantitative data, using a 1-5 Likert scale, from very agree (very satisfied) to disagree (not satisfied). This study examines the "Effect of Motivation, Work Discipline, and Organizational Culture on the performance of employees of PT. Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction).

2.3. Population and Sample

The population in this study were employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction) Karawang 110 people, with a sample of 86 respondents (using the Slovin formula with an error limit or a margin of error of 5%).

2.4. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis method uses descriptive analysis method, Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test, hypothesis testing using t-test and coefficient of determination analysis. Data processing techniques use version 25 of the Statistical Package for Social Studies (SPSS) software.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

Based on the results of this study the basic characteristics of respondents are as follows: 1) Respondents male sex 58.2% and women 41.8%, 2) Respondents aged <30 years 37.3% and > 30 years 62.7%. 3) Education Respondents from high school graduates 17.5%, Diploma 44.2%, scholars 38.3%.

3.2. Hypothesis Testing

3.2.1. Validity and Reliability Test

Test validity using a 95% confidence level, where $df = n - 2$. The value of n in this study is 86, so the value of $df = 84$. With the value of r table = 0.213. Based on the validity test, the results of the study show that on all research variables, each indicator in each dimension is known to r count > r table 0,213, then all research variables namely motivation, work discipline and organizational culture are declared valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test uses the Cronbach Alpha statistical test. Based on the test results it is known that in all research variables both dependent and independent variables, Alpha Cronbach numbers > 0.60. Therefore, this research variable can be stated reliably and items in the variables that are feasible are used as measurement instruments.

3.2.2. Test of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Next Regression analysis is one analysis that aims to determine the effect of a variable on other variables

Table 1: Test Results for Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.130	3.004		1.375	.173
Motivation (X1)	.254	.042	.420	6.059	.000
Work Discipline (X2)	.161	.055	.201	2.912	.005
Organizational Culture (X3)	.339	.060	.407	5.669	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Primary Data Processed (2019)

From the table above it is known, if there is no change in the Work Motivation variable (X1), Work Discipline (X2) and Organizational Culture (X3), or each variable value 0 then the employee performance value of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction) experiences increase of 4,130. If there is an increase there is a Work Motivation variable (X1) of or unit, then the Employee Performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.254 times and or vice versa, assuming the Work Discipline variable (X2) and Organizational Culture (X3) remain. If there is an increase in the Work Discipline variable (X2) of one - unit, then the Employee Performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.161 times and / or vice versa, assuming the variable Work Motivation (X1) and the Organizational Culture variable (X3) remain. If there is an increase in the Organizational Culture (X3) variable of one unit, then the Employee Performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.339 times and / or vice versa, assuming the Work Discipline variable (X2) and Work Motivation (X1) remain.

3.2.3. Determination Coefficient

The coefficient of determination because statistical calculations have two independent variables, you should use Adjusted R Square. The results of the regression statistical output in this study obtained 0.744, this explains that the contribution provided by the variables of motivation, work discipline and organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction) was 74.4%.

Partial Test (t test): The following are the results of the t test to determine the effect of the variable Work Motivation (X1), Work Discipline (X2) and Organizational Culture (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) partially (individually).

Table 2: Partial Test Results (t test)

Model	Coefficients ^a	
	t	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.375	.173
Motivation	6.059	.000
Discipline	2.912	.005
Culture	5.669	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE

Source: Primary Data Processed (2019)

From the table above, it is known where: n = number of data, p = number of independent variables (X) then $(df) = 86 - 3 - 1 = 82$ and for $t(0.05: 82)$ the t table is 1.989. 1) Work Motivation Variables (6,059) greater than t table (1,989) H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, then the Motivation variable has an influence on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction). 2) Work Discipline Variables (2,912) greater than t table (1,989) H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, then the discipline variable has an influence on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction). 3) Organizational Culture Variables (5,669) greater t table (1,989) H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, then the organizational culture variable has an influence on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction).

3.3. Discussion

Based on the results of the study show that motivation has an influence on performance. This means that these variables do have an influence in efforts to improve performance and should be an important concern for the leadership to achieve the targets set by management. The results of the t test and r test show that the effect of motivation on performance is the strongest, so it can be concluded that the motivation of employees in the form of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation will be able to improve employee performance. Based on the correlation on the motivation variable with performance having the strongest influence, it means that it is imperative for the organization to give respect or attention to employee performance, namely Employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction) to increase motivation so as to improve the quality of employee performance output. This result is corroborated by previous studies conducted by Dally Sukmawati (17), that motivation can certainly influence performance, even though it is not the only factor that shapes performance. This quote can be interpreted that motivation is a variable that can affect one's performance. So that the motivation factor cannot be ignored either by the management.

3.3.1. Effect of Work Discipline (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

Based on the results of research work discipline has an influence on employee performance. This means that work discipline variables do have an influence in efforts to improve employee performance. The results of the r test and t test show that the bottom of the work discipline has a strong influence on employee performance, so it is important for leaders and management to avoid negligence, irregularities or omissions that cause waste in doing work that should have imposed strict sanctions on late employees or not enter work without information. The results of this study support previous research conducted by Sherly Shelviana (15), the better the discipline carried out by employees in a company, the greater the work performance that can be generated. The quote can be interpreted that discipline is the most important operational function of human resource management because the better the work discipline of employees, the better the performance that can be achieved.

3.3.2. Effect of Organizational Culture (X3) on Employee Performance (Y)

Based on the results of the study shows that work culture has a strong influence on employee performance. This means that these variables have influence in an effort to improve employee

performance and should be a concern for the leadership in order to maintain the quality and quantity set by management. The results of the r test and t test show that the influence of organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this study support previous research conducted by UmiWitaZahriyah (15), stating that organizational culture can have significant effects on work performance in the long run. The quote can be interpreted that organizational culture can influence and improve the performance of employees, because the system of values and norms that are formed by the members is available so that they only need to implement it.

3.3.3. Effect of Motivation (X1), Work Discipline (X2) and Organizational Culture (X3) together on Employee Performance (Y)

Based on multiple linear regression tests, it is known that simultaneous tests show there is an influence along motivation, work discipline and organizational culture on employee performance, this shows that the more motivation, work discipline and organizational culture of employees at PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (division Customer Satisfaction) results improve on employee performance. This is evident from the determination coefficient value of R Square which states the shared contribution of motivation, work discipline and organizational culture to increase employee performance by 0.744. This figure can be interpreted that 74.4% of the variance in the variable employee performance can be predicted by motivation variables, work discipline and organizational culture while 25.5% comes from other independent variables as determinants of high employee performance.

After testing the hypothesis in multiple regression analysis proved positively and significantly there is an influence of motivation, work discipline and organizational culture on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (division Customer Satisfaction). The phenomenon of the three independent variables namely motivation, work discipline and organizational culture gives a very significant influence on employee performance in other words if you want to improve performance that can improve products (results) of a company, the company cannot produce these three variables, even in managerial concepts must be increased to a higher level.

4. Conclusions and Suggestions

4.1. Conclusion

Based on the test results of Motivation, Work Discipline and Organizational Culture have a positive and significant influence on the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction). This means that the stronger the organizational culture, the stronger the effect on employee behavior will ultimately improve the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (Division Customer Satisfaction).

4.2. Suggestion

Based on the results of this study, it is recommended that PT. Sharp Electronics Indonesia does the following: 1) Creating individual KPIs (key performance indicators). 2) Making disciplinary

variables as one of the KPI assessment (Key Performance Indicators) employees. 3) Carry out activities such as training or seminars and togetherness events such as outbound, so that it is expected to improve the achievement of team performance. 3) It is expected that the next researcher who will conduct the research must be considered about the things that affect the performance of employees of PT Sharp Electronics Indonesia (division Customer Satisfaction). It is recommended to use other variables that are possible as a comparison with the results of this study and the existing theory.

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